

Fig. 1

side of above equation corresponds to Flory's equation and the first two terms together is similar to empirical equation of Mooney. But in our equation, unlike Mooneys, there is no unknown parameter. The curves from first (Curve C) approximation (Flory's) and from the second approximation (Curve B which is similar to Mooney's) have been compared with the curves from a typical experimental result^{9,10} and the curve 'A' from our general equation (3). The theoretical curves are for $n=50$ and $T=300^\circ\text{K}$. The experimental curve is for $n=40$ and $T=300^\circ\text{K}$, approximately.

The theoretical results from Flory and others^{3,4} (which came out as first approximation) and existing experimental results seem to support the new statistical approach to the theory of rubber elasticity.

I would like to express my gratitude to Professor Sadhan Basu, University College of Science, Calcutta for his kind encouragement, suggestion and finally checking the mathematical work.

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Colorimetric Determination of Organotrithiocarbonates and Mercaptans (via Trithiocarbonate Formation)

BALBIR CHAND VERMA*, ŚWATANTAR KUMAR and VIJAY SHARMA

Chemistry Department, Himachal Pradesh University, Simla-171 005 (India)

Manuscript received 16 May 1977, revised 18 March 1978, accepted 8 May 1978

ORGANOTRITHIOCARBONATES may be considered as salts of the corresponding trithiocarbonic acids(I) and are characterised

by the presence of $-\text{C}-\text{S}^-$ group. In spite of the numerous valuable applications of organotrithiocarbonates in industry, medicine and agriculture, their estimation did not attract much attention. Verma and coworkers¹⁻⁶ have very recently developed various aqueous and non-aqueous redox methods for the determination of organotrithiocarbonates. In aqueous medium the methods were also extended to the determination of mercaptans after their quantitative transformation (with carbon disulphide and alkali) into organotrithiocarbonates.

Organotrithiocarbonates react with nickel(II) in slightly acidic medium to form brown coloured precipitates, which can be brought into solutions in the presence of acetone. The absorbance of the yellowish-brown coloured solution thus obtained can be measured photometrically. These observations have been exploited to develop a colorimetric method for the determination of small quantities of organotrithiocarbonates. The method has also been extended to the determination of mercaptans after their quantitative transformation into organotrithiocarbonates. The proposed methods are simple, accurate and reliable. The procedure is less time-consuming and may be used for routine analysis.

Experimental

Organotrithiocarbonates were prepared as described earlier⁸. The purity of the compounds was checked by non-aqueous redox titration¹. The mercaptans (Fluka, Switzerland) were distilled twice before use. All other reagents used in this investigation were of guaranteed quality. Erma Photoelectric Colorimeter (Model A. E. 11), Japan was used for absorbance measurements.

* For correspondence

Determination of Organotrithiocarbonates : Acetone (4 ml) was added to a solution of nickel acetate (2 ml of 0.05N in water) and acetic acid (0.1 ml of 0.1N in water). Different aliquots of trithiocarbonate solution were then slowly added to it while stirring. After adding water (3 ml), the total volume of the mixture solution was made up to 10 ml with acetone. The absorbance of the yellowish-brown solution thus obtained was measured using 420 nm filter against a reagent blank. The results as calculated from the calibration data are given in Table 1.

Determination of Mercaptans : Different aliquots of solutions in acetonitrile of each mercaptan were taken. Each aliquot was treated with 0.5 ml of carbon disulphide and 2 ml of potassium hydroxide (app. 0.05N solution in water). The solution was neutralized with 0.1N acetic acid and transferred to a solution containing nickel acetate (2 ml) and acetic acid (0.1 ml). The volume of the solution was made up to 10 ml with acetone and the absorbance of the yellowish-brown solution thus obtained was measured using 420 nm filter against a reagent blank. The results as calculated from the calibration data are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1.—COLORIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF ORGANO-TRITHIOCARBONATES (TTC) AND MERCAPTANS

Compounds	Amount taken, mg	Amount found, mg	Error, %
<i>Organotrithiocarbonates (potassium salts)</i>			
Ethyl TTC	0.484	0.482	-0.41
	0.655	0.658	0.45
	0.836	0.832	-0.47
Isopropyl TTC	0.578	0.581	0.52
	0.770	0.766	-0.53
	0.962	0.962	0.00
<i>n</i> -Propyl TTC	0.942	0.937	-0.52
	1.167	1.162	-0.42
	1.885	1.878	-0.27
Isobutyl TTC	0.493	0.493	0.00
	0.783	0.781	-0.25
	1.399	1.403	0.29
<i>n</i> -Butyl TTC	0.232	0.231	-0.43
	0.580	0.582	0.34
	0.926	0.924	-0.21
<i>n</i> -Amyl TTC	0.456	0.453	-0.65
	0.647	0.645	-0.31
	1.124	1.127	0.26
Benzyl TTC	0.206	0.205	-0.48
	0.516	0.518	0.38
	1.032	1.028	-0.38
<i>Mercaptans</i>			
Ethyl mercaptan	0.127	0.128	0.78
	0.205	0.206	0.48
	0.280	0.278	-0.71
Isopropyl mercaptan	0.231	0.232	0.43
	0.308	0.306	-0.65
	0.385	0.385	0.00
<i>n</i> -Propyl mercaptan	0.214	0.213	-0.46
	0.324	0.325	0.31
	0.377	0.379	0.53
Isobutyl mercaptan	0.225	0.226	0.44
	0.286	0.286	0.00
	0.371	0.370	-0.24
<i>n</i> -Butyl mercaptan	0.157	0.158	0.63
	0.251	0.253	0.79
	0.314	0.316	0.63
<i>n</i> -Amyl mercaptan	0.184	0.183	-0.54
	0.273	0.275	0.73
	0.334	0.336	0.60
Benzyl mercaptan	0.162	0.161	-0.61
	0.324	0.322	-0.62
	0.583	0.585	0.34

Results and Discussion

The results recorded in Table 1 show that the proposed method for the determination of organotrithiocarbonates gives accurate and reproducible results with a maximum error of 0.7%. The colour development of their nickel salts is instantaneous, and remains stable for about 10 minutes. This method is sensitive as well as precise. Sodium sulphide, urea, acetate, sulphate, carbonate and carbon disulphide do not cause any interference when present in small amounts. Xanthates, dithiocarbamates and amines, however, interfere.

The determination of mercaptans after their quantitative transformation (with carbon disulphide and potassium hydroxide) into the corresponding organotrithiocarbonates, excess of carbon disulphide does not cause any interference in the determinations which have been effected with a maximum error of 0.8%. Alcohols and amines (primary and secondary), however, interfere due to the expected formation of xanthates and dithiocarbamates respectively under the experimental conditions.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Council of Scientific and Industrial Research for the award of research fellowship to one of them (S.K.).

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